

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

This report presents the evaluation of key performance metrics in SR-ESMs with improved representation of the oceanic and atmospheric boundary layers with a focus on the tropics and on the Southern Ocean.

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WP7

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Executive summary

The main objective of WP6 has been to tune the existing ocean and atmospheric boundary layer schemes for the forced ocean and the atmosphere components of the ICON and IFS-FESOM Storm-resolving ESMs (SREMS). This allowed for detailed investigations of mixing processes, because turbulence observations are available for a particular storm. The objective of the present D7.4 is now to evaluate how these boundary layer schemes affect the representation of climate in the nextGEMS coupled systems. As in WP6 we find that the details of the boundary layer schemes do not much affect the existing biases so that the ultimate choice of the boundary layer schemes in both, atmosphere and ocean, are determined by practical considerations:

- future IFS simulations will continue to use K-profile theory to parameterize boundary layer turbulence and eddy-diffusive mass-flux to parameterize turbulence and cloud formation in the boundary layer. This is motivated by the high accuracy, a key objective for operational agencies like ECMWF.
- future ICON-A simulations will avoid physics parameterizations beyond the Smagorinsky closure to dissipate energy at the grid scale. This makes the model physics and dynamics transparent and turns ICON-A into an ideal research tool.
- future IFS-FESOM simulations will be done with the K-profile parameterization (KPP), because it provides a realistic 20th century increase in global temperatures. The alternative scheme, the Turbulent Kinetic Energy (TKE) parameterization mixes too much, which results in unrealistic 20th century warming.
- future ICON-O simulation will be done with the TKE scheme for two reasons: it is energy based (rather than the empirical KPP), which allows easy combination with the abyssal mixing scheme IDEMIX, and KPP is licensed under GNU, which would limit further applications.

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Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	yes

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no
O3	
To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:	
(i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and	no
(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	no

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP7	Relevance in this deliverable?
To identify the importance of meso-scale air-sea interaction on tropical climate, on its dominant patterns of variability and teleconnections, and on its response to global warming (O1,O2)	no
To appraise the significance of resolving atmospheric convection and storm-scales for simulating the West African Monsoon (WAM) and hydrological cycle extremes, and their response to global warming (O1,O2)	no
To evaluate the influence of mesoscales on tropical cyclones and on their response to global warming. (O2)	no
To assess the impacts of climate and climate change on global primary productivity, and global and West African fisheries using SR-ESMs (O1,O2,O3)	no
To anticipate the relevance of resolving mesoscale circulations for global climate change assessments (O1,O2,O3)	no
To evaluate and refine new ocean mixed layer and planetary boundary layer representation in the coupled system (O1)	yes

1 Deliverable 7.4 for Task 7.5

WP6 has provided a good first guess of how the representation of the ocean mixed layer and the planetary boundary layer needs to be improved in SR-ESMs. In WP6 some of the developments (to the ocean mixed layer) were tested mainly in forced ocean integrations. In this task, the ideas developed in WP6 for mixing both in the ocean and planetary boundary layer will be tested in a coupled framework (sections 2 and 3 below). This adds a new dimension to the complexity of the problem, and one main focus of the analysis will hence be on the co-evolution of surface momentum, freshwater and heat fluxes with SST and mixed layer depth. Because of its importance for the uptake of anthropogenic CO₂, a secondary focus will be the co-evolution of atmosphere and upper ocean during storms over the Southern Ocean (section 4) Regarding the atmosphere, the main focus will be on shallow convection and how the planetary boundary layer and its parameterizations affect atmospheric variability and convection regimes, in particular in the tropical region covered by EUREC4A (section 5).

2 Ocean mixing and Tropical Precipitation

To investigate the impact of the ML parameterizations on the mean climate we focus on precipitation. This is because over the few decades over which we can afford to run SRESMs only the tropical upper ocean is spun-up (Liu et al., 1994), and precipitation reacts strongly to even minor changes in SST gradients (Jochum, 2009). From the WP6 work we learned that the OGCMs are not too sensitive to the details of the parameterization schemes (Bastin and coauthors, 2025), so that the main focus here is to make sure that coupled effects do not lead to surprises. The following integrations are analyzed:

From the stand-alone ocean simulations executed for WP6 we learned that the length of the simulations should be longer than the few years achievable with the full-blown nextGEMS cycle 4 set-ups. Therefore we decided to run the sensitivity experiments using the same resolution in the ocean as in WP6, but apply much lower resolution in the atmosphere. The following configurations were used:

ICON: 80km atmosphere, 10km ocean, TKE ML model (it was decided to abandon KPP, see executive summary);

mss009: 1950-2014 with a $c_k = 0.1$ and no minimum background diffusivity. c_k determines how much of the TKE is converted in mixing (here 10%), the background diffusivity is the result of internal wave breaking in the abyssal ocean ($0.17 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$, Ledwell et al., 1998).

mss010: branched off from mss009 at year 1979, with $c_k = 0.2$, and

mss011: like mss010 but with $c_k = 0.1$ and a background diffusivity of $0.17 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$.

The ICON precipitation (Figure 1b) shows the typical double ITCZ bias, i.e., there is a second band of strong precipitation south of the equator (Figure 1a,c) in both the Atlantic and Pacific. This bias is worse when the background diffusivity is removed in mss09 (Figure 1e), in particular

Figure 1: Observed precipitation (a), precipitation simulated by ICON (b), and the biases in mss011 (c), all in mm/day. The impact of the various parameter choices are displayed on the right panels and discussed in the text.

in the Atlantic, although the biases in the Indian and Pacific warm pool are reduced (see the red in 1e to east and west of Indonesia). Thus, while it is certainly more in line with the observations, a background diffusivity provides no clear benefit in the coupled model. The integration with an enhanced value of c_k (mss10) shows very similar differences to mss11, only larger (Figure 1f). However, it is important to realize that the precipitation changes that can be achieved by - for the ocean quite important, see Bastin et al. 2025 - modifications of the mixed layer schemes are only a fraction of the prevailing biases.

IFS-FESOM: 35km atmosphere, 10km ocean, both TKE and KPP models, 1950-2014. An additional KPP integration as made to investigate the impact of increased background diffusivity (1 instead of $0.1 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$) in the Indonesian Seas. Observations find values that are an order of magnitude larger than in the open ocean, because the energy of the tides becomes trapped there. Numerical simulations suggest that this leads to reorganization of the precipitation over

Figure 2: Global mean surface air temperature trend for IFS-F/TKE (black) and IFS-F/KPP (red/blue).

Figure 3: Precipitation bias in IFS-F/KPP. Note the lack of equatorial precipitation and its excess precipitation south of it.

the Pacific warm pool (Jochum and Potemra, 2008).

Choosing the TKE scheme leads to an unrealistic temperature trend, whereas with KPP IFS-FESOM reproduces the observed trend during the analysis period (Figure 2, the two KPP simulations differ in the details of the sea-ice formulation, which does not affect the trend). An analysis of the precipitation fields suggests that KPP does not deliver worse precipitation fields. Figure 3 shows IFS-F (KPP) precipitation biases similar to other ESMs (e.g. Small and coauthors, 2014): too little rain along the Pacific equator and too much to the north of it, and there is too much rain south of the equator in the Atlantic and Pacific (the double-ITCZ problem). TKE makes the summer bias in the Atlantic worse, but the warm pool bias in the winter better (Figure 4). But the magnitude of either differences are only a fraction of the overall biases. Thus, for IFS-FESOM, KPP has been chosen as default.

Figure 4: Difference in precipitation between IFS-F/TKE and /KPP. Note the difference in the color bars between the present and the previous figure.

Increasing the background mixing in the Indonesian Seas does, as in coarse ESMs, reduce the precipitation biases in the warm pool (Figure 5): the increased mixing there leads to slightly reduced SST (not shown) and a corresponding eastward shift of the warmpool precipitation, leading regionally to a 30% reduction in biases in the winter.

3 Bayesian Optimization

From WP6 and the previous section it has become clear that it pays to care about the details of ML schemes, but much to our disappointment fundamental biases like the double ITCZ still remain. Thus, we decided to leave our physical intuition behind and develop an automated parameter-tuning algorithm that optimizes the whole set of uncertain parameters in one go: Veropt, a Bayesian optimization tool for Python/Jax based ocean models. The current version can utilize the GPUs of the EuroHPC LUMI (<https://www.lumi-supercomputer.eu/>) and delivers an optimized 9-dimensional parameter space for a 1 degree ocean model in a week (Mrozowska and coauthors, 2025). By August we expect to be able to apply Veropt to fully coupled Fortran-based climate models, which allow us to finally eliminate the double ITCZ biases prevalent in all climate models. Provided enough computing resources (requests are pending) Veropt can then be applied to SRESMs like ICON as well.

Standard parameter optimization for ESMs relies on a seasoned expert, who decides which of the model parameters most affect the desired outcome (here: c_k in TKE will affect tropical precipitation). Integrations with different parameter values are then performed and outcomes are compared (see previous section). This is time consuming and important parameters may be overlooked. However, simply trying all possible combinations of all parameter values is too expensive. Thus, in Veropt an initial set of random parameter choices is used to create an estimate of the topology of the model error. Based on this topology new parameter values are chosen, and the process is repeated until the model error converges to a minimum. The success

Figure 5: Precipitation biases in IFS-F/KPP for austral winter (upper left) and summer (lower left), and the effect of increasing the diapycnal diffusivity in the Indonesian Seas during winter (upper right) and summer (lower right) [mm/day].

of this method does depend on the real topology of the model error (see Mrozowska et al. 2025 for the technical details), but our present results suggest that for climate models this method is a promising way forward.

A single LUMI GPU nodes has 32 GPUs, each one can host a 1x1 degree ocean model integration. After 20 iterations, each one being 32 70 year simulations in parallel, we were able to improve significantly the ML depth, through an unexpected combination of 3 bulk-flux coefficients, 2 parameters of the implementation of thickness diffusion (Eden and Greatbatch, 2008), and 4 parameters of the TKE scheme (Figure 6). Apart from MLD errors, the loss function contained the strengths of AMOC and ACC, as well as the depth of the 18°C isotherm to avoid that MLD improvements are achieved at the cost of other key model states. In particular, the improvement in the Southern Ocean alleviates a long-standing bias of OGCMs, which suggests that longstanding biases in the coupled model can be improved as well.

4 Carbon fluxes and mesoscale turbulence in the Southern Ocean

We examined the role of storms in the Southern Ocean for the oceanic uptake of carbon dioxide (CO₂). To this end, we took advantage of a one-year, coupled ICON simulation run with the HAMOCC ocean-biogeochemistry component. The model configuration for this simulation is identical to the nextgems cycle 3 simulations, but the horizontal grid spacing is 5 km for both ocean and atmosphere. Storm metrics, such as tropical cyclone frequency and tropical cyclone days, in the ICON cycle 3 (5km) simulation was found to be in good agreement with observations (see nextGEMS Deliverable 6.1). Prior to coupling with the atmosphere, the ocean is spun up with 5-km atmosphere forcing from 2010 to 2017 and then together with HAMOCC from 2017

Figure 6: Zonal average of annual mean mixed layer depth for the observations (solid black line), the default model configuration (dotted line) and the simulations with the 26 best parameter sets (red). Note that the best sets reduce the MLD in high latitudes and reduce it in low latitudes, both being an improvement.

to 2020 (see <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/DYAMOND/NextGEMS/prefinal.html>, exp. ngc3542).

We first tracked the storms by applying the TRACK algorithm (Hodges, 1994) on hourly model data of mean sea-level pressure. Subsequently, we evaluated storm statistics against a climatology derived from ERA-Interim reanalysis data (Wei and Qin, 2016). Finally, we selected a single storm as a case study to gain insight into the impact of storms in the Southern Ocean on CO₂ fluxes. We chose an intense storm that reached hurricane strength, where surface wind speeds exceed 33 m/s. Then we analysed anomalies of mean sea-level pressure, 10-m wind speed, sea-surface temperature (SST), DIC, pCO₂ and CO₂ flux at the air-sea interface. To relate changes in these fields with the storm, we calculated the anomalies in storm-centric coordinates with the reference period taken as the average over the 10 days prior to the storm's arrival.

The simulation displays sensible storm statistics. The number of simulated storms for each of the seasons deviates by less than 10% from the climatological values. In addition, the ICON model is able to simulate a maximum in storm activity in the austral Winter, which is consistent with observations. A Hovmoeller plot with the anomalies calculated in storm-centric coordinates is shown in Figure 7. The storm is visible as a negative anomaly in the mean sea-level pressure and a positive wind-speed anomaly (Figure 7a,b). The area traversed by the storm experiences a successive decrease in SST (Figure 1c). At the same time, DIC increases at the ocean surface (Figure 1d). Changes in both SST and DIC contribute inter alia to changes in pCO₂ (Figure 7e). The pCO₂ anomalies experience an increase several days before the storm is directly overhead (0 hours) and then decreases steadily. This change in tendency suggests that the

Figure 7: Hovmoeller plots of averaged anomalies for a) mean sea-level pressure, b) 10-m wind speed, c) SST, d) DIC, e) ocean pCO₂ and f) CO₂ flux. Each data point is calculated by averaging the corresponding anomaly field over a 20 x 20 degree latitude-longitude box centered on a given track point. The time elapsed in hours since the storm's arrival at a given track point is plotted on the x-axis. The date associated with each track point along the storm's trajectory is plotted on the y-axis. For a given track point on the y-axis, the location of the box is fixed and the storm moves eastward across the box. At time 0 hours, the storm is centered on the corresponding box. Note that the temporal resolution for the upper two panels is hourly, whereas the remaining panels are based on daily data. Here a positive value for CO₂ flux corresponds to less ocean uptake compared to the reference period.

pCO₂ anomalies are initially dominated by increasing DIC that acts to increase pCO₂, and then by decreasing SST, which tends to decrease pCO₂. The opposite tendencies of DIC and SST is consistent with the limited range of observations of storms in the Southern Ocean (Carranza and coauthors, 2024, Nicholson and coauthors, 2022). Changes in pCO₂ driven by the storm contribute to the CO₂ flux anomalies at the air-sea interface (Figure 7f). It should be noted that the absolute values of CO₂ flux remain negative throughout, corresponding to ocean uptake of CO₂ (not shown). Overall, the storm is primarily associated with positive CO₂ flux anomalies for the time slice shown, corresponding to a reduction in CO₂ uptake. The positive pCO₂ anomalies

prior to the storm are consistent with a positive CO₂ flux anomaly (i.e. less uptake). However, the subsequent reduction in oceanic pCO₂ values does not coincide with a reduction in the CO₂ flux anomaly. One possible reason that requires further analysis is that the reduction in uptake stems from the drop in the wind speed lowering the gas transfer velocity, a monotonically increasing function of wind speed that scales the CO₂ flux at the air-sea interface.

5 Atmospheric Boundary Layer off Barbados

This project evaluates the representation of shallow convection and boundary-layer properties in the tropical oceans in nextGEMS simulations. The simulation's initialization was aligned with the EUREC⁴A field campaign, starting on 20 Jan 2020. This allowed us to validate simulations against measurements obtained during the field campaign in the tropical Atlantic trade-winds region upwind of Barbados. The simulations considered the ICON and IFS models performing numerical experiments with distinct grid spacings and parameterization schemes. The observational campaign includes dropsonde measurements at a circular airborne-sounding array windward of Barbados. This dataset provides divergence and vertical velocity data, which allowed a recent study to present observational evidence of the shallow mesoscale overturning circulations (SMOCs) (George et al., 2023).

Measurements

The observational data was measured during the EUREC⁴A (Elucidating the Role of Clouds Circulation Coupling in Climate) field campaign (Bony et al., 2017; Stevens et al., 2021), which took place in the Atlantic trade-winds region east of Barbados during January and February 2020. Initially, EUREC⁴A was presented to test hypothesized cloud-feedback mechanisms believed to explain large discrepancies in model estimates of climate sensitivity and provide benchmark data for a new generation of satellite observations and models (Bony et al., 2017). High Altitude and Long Range Research Aircraft (HALO) was used to characterize the clouds and cloud environment from above, using remote sensing and dropsondes (Stevens et al., 2021).

HALO operated at an altitude of about 10 km, primarily following a fixed circular flight path known as the EUREC⁴A-circle (Stevens et al., 2021). This path, centered at 13.31° N, 57.67° W, had a diameter of 223 km (George et al., 2021). Flights were made independently of meteorological conditions, and times were adjusted to best sample the diel cycle. However, given operational constraints, HALO was mainly restricted to daylight hours. In one circuit around the EUREC⁴A-circle, 12 dropsondes were launched in about one hour, resulting in sonde launches separated by about 5 min (George et al., 2021). Most HALO flight days had a typical flight pattern of two sets of 3 circles (circling set) separated by a one-hour excursion aimed at sampling upwind conditions while the ATR aircraft refueled (Stevens et al., 2021). The first target of the HALO flight strategy was the measurement for each EUREC⁴A-circle of the vertical profile of mass divergence using dropsondes (Stevens et al., 2021) to allow accurate estimations of the mean vertical motion (George et al., 2021). The dropsondes were also used to characterize the thermodynamic structure in the region (George et al., 2021).

The dataset JOANNE (Joint dropsonde Observations of the Atmosphere in tropical North at-

laNtic mesoscale Environments) provides measurements from the EUREC⁴A's HALO dropsondes (George et al., 2021). The JOANNE Level-3 (L3) dataset has dropsonde measurements interpolated onto a uniform vertical grid of 10 m spacing. The main goal of the L3 product is to grid all soundings onto the same vertical grid, simplifying their application for various analyses. The Level-4 (L4) product offers circle products as gradient terms estimated by regressing the parameters at each level considering the circle's sondes. Additionally, the L4 product provides terms of vorticity, divergence, and vertical velocity, which are calculated from the gradient terms.

In atmospheric sciences, two types of vertical velocity are used to describe vertical motion: the vertical velocity expressed in height coordinates (w in m/s^{-1}) and the vertical velocity expressed in pressure coordinates (ω in Pa/s^{-1}). The first directly measures the rate of ascent or descent of air in terms of physical height, and a positive w indicates upward motion as the altitude increases as it goes up. The former measures the rate of pressure change as the air moves vertically, and a negative ω indicates upward motion as the pressure lowers as it goes up.

Simulations

The nextGEMS simulations were initialized on 20 January 2020 to align with the EUREC⁴A field campaign, in the same way as the winter DYNamics of the Atmospheric general circulation Modeled On Non-hydrostatic Domains (DYAMOND) intercomparison study (Hohenegger et al., 2023). The only exception is the ICON Cycle 4 simulation, which was initialized on the first of January 2020.

Each model used a different configuration and performed simulations with distinct horizontal resolutions. The nextGEMS models are described in detail in Hohenegger et al., 2023 and Rackow et al., 2024, and the main characteristics of the simulations related to the present work are described in Table 3. The model results are saved with distinct time frequencies and, in the case of IFS, with fewer vertical levels than those used during the simulations (Table 4). Although IFS simulations are performed with 137 vertical levels (Table 3), only 23 levels are saved as the output (Table 4). Considering the 137 vertical levels in the IFS, there are 31 levels below 3 km. Regarding vertical velocities, ICON computes and outputs it in height coordinates (w) (Hohenegger et al., 2023), while IFS computes and outputs it in pressure coordinates (ω) (ECMWF, 2023). For the analysis in the present work, ω was computed for ICON, and w was computed for IFS as post-processing based on the respective variables from the model output.

Simulation results were extracted to compare with the observations, and the sampling strategy depended on whether it was the L3 or L4 dataset. For JOANNE L3 variables, the simulation data was extracted from the model grid points nearest the dropsondes launch location and time. For JOANNE L4 variables, the model data was extracted considering the closest time of the L4 variable and averaged over a square bounding the EUREC⁴A-Circle. The square comprises 2852 grid points for the IFS4-FESOM5, 1222 for ngc3028, 702 for IFS9-FESOM5, 312 for ngc4008 and IFS9-FESOM5-production, and 21 for ERA5. In the present work, we analyzed the period from 21 January to 3 February 2020. The start date (21 January 2020) was chosen to allow for a one-day spin-up period following the initialization of the nextGEMS simulations. The period ended on 3 February 2020 to keep the simulation results influenced by the model's initial conditions. We examined six flights with six circles each, totaling 36 circles, and about 400 dropsonde launches within this period. During this time frame, there were flights every two days. Since the

Table 3: Characteristics of the nextGEMS simulations. The columns show (from left to right) the nextGEMS development cycle, simulation short name, atmospheric model, approximate horizontal grid spacing (Δx), number of vertical levels, number of vertical levels below 3 km height, turbulence model, use of the deep convection, and shallow convection schemes.

Cycle	Simulation	Model	Δx	#lev	#lev <3 km	Turbulence scheme	Deep convec.	Shallow convec.
3	ngc3028	ICON	5 km	91	18	Smagorinsky	off	off
4	ngc4008	ICON	10 km	91	18	Smagorinsky	off	off
3	IFS4- FESOM5	IFS	4 km	137	31	K theory and EDMF*	on "1/5"	on
3	IFS9- FESOM5	IFS	9 km	137	31	K theory and EDMF*	on	on
4	IFS9- FESOM5 -production	IFS	9 km	137	31	K theory and EDMF*	on "1/6"	on

*Eddy-Diffusivity Mass-Flux

Table 4: Characteristics of the nextGEMS simulations output. The columns show (from left to right) the nextGEMS development cycle, simulation short name, atmospheric model, output type, number of vertical levels, number of vertical levels below 3 km height, and output frequency of the two-dimensional (2D) and three-dimensional (3D) data.

Cycle	Simulation	Model	Output type	#lev	#lev <3 km	Frequency output
3	ngc3028	ICON	HEALPix grid (zoom = 10)	91	18	2D data: 30m 3D data: 3h
4	ngc4008	ICON	HEALPix grid (zoom = 9)	91	18	2D data: 15m 3D data: 24h
3	IFS4- FESOM5	IFS	native	23	10	2D data: 1h 3D data: 6h
3	IFS9- FESOM5	IFS	native	23	10	2D data: 1h 3D data: 6h
4	IFS9- FESOM5 -production	IFS	HEALPix grid (zoom = 9)	23	10	2D data: 1h 3D data: 1h

first flight after 21 January took place on 22 January, the model results from the first two days were not considered in the analysis.

Results

The humidity, temperature, and wind variability across the Circle result from a combination of atmospheric convective systems, turbulent fluctuations (Iyer et al., 2022), and sea surface temperature gradients (Fernández et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2023). However, there are some average patterns in the Circle. For instance, (Savazzi et al., 2022) found that the winds are stronger at the cloud base (500 m) in the southeast region, while (Iyer et al., 2022) reported that the sea surface temperature is warmer in the southwest region.

During the EUREC⁴A campaign, the near-surface northeasterly winds prevailed on average, but both southerly and northerly meridional components were observed along the time (Savazzi et al., 2022). During the analysis period of this work, the first day exhibited a northerly meridional component, whereas, in the following days, the southerly meridional component prevailed. Regarding the vertical variability, climatologically, easterly winds dominate below around 3 km, where there is a transition to westerly winds (George et al., 2021). This reversal was present in the measurements, with the westerly more evident and shallower in the third and fourth analysis days (not shown).

The mean vertical profiles represent the winter-time trade-wind boundary layer (Fig. 8). The simulated profiles of potential temperature, specific humidity, relative humidity, and wind speed are roughly similar to the observed vertical structure and qualitatively capture its primary features. Both the observations and simulations show a well-mixed sub-cloud layer with high wind speeds below about 600 m and a moist layer extending up to around 2 km. Regarding the specific humidity profile, ICON better represented the shape of the sub-cloud layer, and both models showed a more continuous transition between the top of the sub-cloud layer (at 600 m) and the free troposphere than JOANNE.

However, the simulations were less accurate in representing the magnitude of the variables. The virtual potential temperature was underestimated in the pre-final simulations, particularly in ICON (around 3 K), but also in IFS (about 1 K). ICON systematically represented a dryer profile, while IFS showed a dryer sub-cloud layer and a moister layer above 2 km. The lower specific humidity can be explained as a thermodynamic response to the colder temperatures since relative humidity stays almost the same in simulations and observations, and cooler air can hold less water vapor (Schulz and Stevens, 2023). The more continuous profile in IFS might be related to more parameterizations smoothing the result.

IFS accurately captured the magnitude of the wind speed, whereas ICON overestimated it considerably. These discrepancies were noted in previous simulation cycles, but the ICON pre-final simulation amplified them. According to JOANNE data, the vertical velocity shows subsidence conditions on average. The pre-final simulations represent, on average, vertical velocities close to zero below the first kilometer, meaning the positive and negative values balance out in these simulations. Above the first kilometer, they appropriately capture the mean subsiding motion. The Cycle 3 IFS simulations accurately represented the vertical velocity sign, while the ICON simulation represented mean upward motion above 2 km.

IFS has a too moist cloud layer and a too dry sub-cloud layer, and ICON the opposite. IFS changes it with the mass flux and ICON with the stability correction. ICON uses the stability correction to change cloud fraction and the TOA balance, whereas IFS uses the convection scheme.

Figure 8: Vertical profiles of (left to right) potential temperature, specific humidity, relative humidity, horizontal wind speed, omega, and vertical velocity for the nextGEMS cycle 3 (ngc3) and pre-final (ngc4) simulations. The solid line shows the average, and the shading shows the standard deviation. Observations are shown in gray, and simulation results are shown in red.

It seems that both are equally good to use: ICON is simpler as it allows to trace back more clearly the tuning to one parameter, in this case the stability function, which hopefully helps to under-

stand more clearly the influence of one process in another. IFS has more parameters because of the mass-flux, which might complicate understanding the interrelation between processes. On the other hand, one would expect that, because IFS has more parameters, one could tune more variables. Hence, ICON might be more helpful for research and IFS more helpful for operational forecast. Thus, they complement each other.

6 Conclusion

This report is the result of some five years of not only model simulations but also of numerous discussions, online and in person, during small meetings or during the hackathons.

On the ocean side the coupled WP7 work further corroborated the surprising results of the forced-ocean WP6 work: the details of the boundary layer schemes do not seem to matter. On the one hand, this can be read as a testament to the community's deep understanding of boundary layer physics, because TKE and KPP are based on radically different approaches: the former solves a turbulent kinetic energy budget, and the latter prescribes a diffusivity profile. Of course, both are strongly constrained by the available kinetic and potential energy (i.e., wind and stratification), and have been tuned against (few) available observations. On the other hand, this lack of sensitivity to details is disappointing, because it voids what at least the present PIs thought would be a powerful tool to improve tropical precipitation. These conclusions find further support from the systematic parameter optimization discussed in section 3: the current TKE parameter are indeed the optimal ones and further improvement of MLDs are most likely to be expected from a better representation of bulk flux formulae - something that also already hinted at in WP6 and Bastin et al. (2025).

In principle the careful and systematic investigation of the connection between mixing physics and MLD would need to be repeated for other important quantities like CO₂. Given the resources available to us we could touch on the connection between resolution and carbon fluxes. Section 4 shows that these fluxes are clearly affected by storms, qualitatively in the same manner as suggestion by observations. There are, however, simply not enough observations and computational resources available to quantify this connection credibly.

On the atmosphere side, the turbulence models were changed in cycles 3 and 4 to fit better with the observations based on the experience in earlier cycles. For instance, ICON focused on the stability function to control the shallow clouds, based on the experience during the early cycles about the strong effect that this component of the turbulence parametrization had in the low-cloud coverage and thereby on the TOA energy balance. This was coordinated with changes in the radiative parametrization (the inhomogeneous factor). Both tuning knobs, stability function and inhomogeneous factor, proved most relevant to obtain an appropriate energy balance, but the low-cloud distribution (shallow vs stratocumulus) still deviates from observations. The results in NextGEMS suggests to further explore different choices of stability functions, given their observed relevance, and explore the extension of the Smagorinsky model with the Leonard terms. This extension has been reported to affect positively the representation of convection (Takasuka and coauthors, 2024), and it is currently being developed in the WarmWorld project.

7 References

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